

Detecting Olympic Tourism Legacy using Structural Change Tests

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Abstract

Tourism legacy has been a main justification for hosting Olympic games, however, questions remain regarding its timing, duration, form, size, and even its existence. Extensive research has been done using various approaches, however, the evidences have not been conclusive. In this paper, using international travel volume as a proxy of tourism, we attempt to contribute a new piece of evidence of the legacy by using structural change tests. Time series models are identified for monthly air travel volume to the host cities of several recent Olympic games, structural change tests are used to detect significant changes in the model structure, changes around the time of the Olympics games indicate tourism legacy, the timing and size of the changes can be estimated. Depending on the data, one of two approaches (monitoring or testing) is used: when it is possible, a model free of structural changes is identified using a pre-game period and used to detect a structural change in the subsequent monitoring period (monitoring); when it is not possible to do so due to insufficient pre-game data, or multiple structural changes in the period of interest, the data covering a few years before and a few years after the games are used to test for structural changes (testing). Various structural change tests including residual-based, estimate-based tests, and the F-tests, are used in monitoring and testing. If evidence of structural changes is found, the number and dates of structural changes are estimated (Dating). Structural changes are found in several of the series analyzed around the time of the Olympics games, which indicates the existence of Olympic tourism legacy.

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1 Introduction

Whether a city should host an Olympic game is often the subject of fierce debates. Olympic legacy has often been used to support hosting the Olympics (Weed, 2014). The idea of Olympic legacy was first proposed by the International Olympic Committee (IOC) in 1988 (Tomlinson, 2014). It has been argued that Olympic legacy takes many forms, including promoting tourism, city revitalization, improved image of the host city, construction of new sporting and tourism facilities, change of policies (Chen et al. 2021), gain in human capital (Kaplanidou et al. 2021), etc. The Olympic tourism legacy is the most important of these and is often used as a major economic justifications for hosting the Olympics (Weed 2014). Olympic legacy has attracted much attention recently, and a lot of research has been done on the various aspects of the legacy, comprehensive reviews of the recent status of the research can be found in Koenigstorfer et al. (2019), Scheu et al. (2021), and Thomson et al. (2019). Preuss and Hong (2021) provided a review focusing on legacy research on the under-researched events, such as the Youth Olympics, winter Games, etc. However, despite numerous empirical studies, the evidence of Olympic tourism legacy has been inconclusive. The Olympic tourism legacy, if exists, will significantly change the level of tourism to the host city. One of the indicators of tourism is the travel volume to the host city. If the Olympic tourism legacy exists, it will be accompanied by significant changes in the travel volume to the host cities around the time of the games. Some researchers argue that the legacy effect starts before the games due to the promotion during the bidding period, some found evidence that travel volume changed significantly during the games, while some found evidence that the effect begins sometime after the games. Evidences of both increase and decrease in the travel volume have been found. The duration of the changes also varies in different studies. In this paper, we use structural change tests to detect if such legacy existed in recent Olympic games, and estimate the timing, the duration, and the size of the legacy. The structural change tests are originally developed for regression models, but they have been shown to be successful in detecting structural changes in time series models (Zeileis et al. 2003, Zeileis et al, 2010). If tourism legacy exists, then the change in travel volume will cause the regression model to change around the time of the games, and such structural changes can be detected using structure change tests. The structural change tests are very flexible, they do not require any assumptions regarding the time, the number, and the nature of the changes, instead, they “let the data speak for themselves” to explore the existence, timing, duration, and size of the change. The asymptotic distributions of the test statistics are well-established, so formal tests can be conducted and confidence intervals can be constructed. The structural tests offer an accurate and reliable method to detect changes in the travel

volume caused by mega events such as the Olympics, however, to our knowledge, they have not been applied to study the Olympic tourism legacy in the literature. In this paper, we attempt to use structural change tests to offer new evidences regarding the existence of Olympic legacy.

The paper is organized as follows: A brief background of the structural change tests is given in Section 2, the results of the monitoring procedure are presented in Section 3, and the results of testing using the whole sample are presented in Section 4. The paper concludes with summary and discussion in Section 5.

2 Structural Change Tests

This section provides some technical background and general ideas of the procedures used in this paper. We will keep the discussion short and refer the readers to the references for more technical details.

The tests for structural changes in linear regression models can be categorized into two types: the tests based on F statistics, such as the the well-known Chow-test and the supF test (Hansen 1992a, Andrews 1993, Andrews and Ploberger 1994); and tests based on the generalized fluctuation process, including the empirical fluctuation tests (the cumulative sum (CUSUM) tests, the moving sum (MOSUM) tests), and the estimates-based tests. Kuan and Honik (1995) provided a unifying view of the empirical fluctuation tests.

The tests are based on the standard linear regression model with k independent variables (X_1, \dots, X_k) :

$$y_t = \beta_{0t} + \beta_{1t}x_{1t} + \dots + \beta_{kt}x_{kt} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

where $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, ε_t are iid with mean of zero and variance σ^2 . Let $\beta_t = (\beta_{0t}, \beta_{1t}, \dots, \beta_{kt})^\tau$ be the vector of the regression coefficients at time t , the null hypothesis of the structural change test is

$$H_0 : \beta_t = \beta_0,$$

for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, and β_0 is the vector of coefficients that does not change over time. Obviously H_0 indicates no structural change over time. The alternative hypothesis is different for different tests. For example, the tests based on the F-statistics are designed for a single break at unknown time, while there is no explicit pattern of departure from the null for the generalized fluctuation tests.

Both the CUSUM and MOSUM tests can be based on recursive residuals or the OLS residuals. They are based on empirical fluctuation processes with known asymptotic distributions. The CUSUM process is based on the cumulative sum of recursive

residuals (Brown et al. 1975) or OLS residuals (Ploberger and Krämer 1992). Under the null hypothesis, when the sample size is large enough, the recursive residual-based CUSUM process is approximately a standard Brownian motion process. Under the alternative of a single structural change, this process has zero mean before the point of change, and departs mean zero afterwards. The limiting process of the OLS residual-based CUSUM process is the standard Brownian bridge, under the alternative of a single change, this process will have a peak around the time of change. Instead of using the cumulative sum of the (recursive or OLS) residuals, empirical fluctuation processes can be based on the sum of residuals in a moving window, the results are the MOSUM processes. The limiting process of the recursive-residual based MOSUM process are the increments of a Brownian motion, and for OLS residual-based MOSUM, the increments of a Brownian bridge. Under the alternative of a single change, both MOSUM processes will have a significant shift around the point of change.

Instead of the residuals, the empirical fluctuation processes can also be calculated using the estimated coefficients of the regression model, the results are the estimate-based processes. The basic idea is to obtain the coefficient estimates using either a growing number of observations (CUSUM, Ploberger et al. 1989), or the observations in a window moving across the whole sample period (MOSUM, Chu et al. 1995b), then compare the CUSUM or the MOSUM estimates with the estimates obtained using the whole sample, if the difference is abnormally large by their respective sampling distribution, then the null of no structural change is rejected. The estimate-based processes are k -dimensional processes, one process for each regression coefficient. This allows for a more detailed view of the nature of the structural change, i.e., is the structural change in the intercept or any specific independent variables. The limiting processes for the recursive estimates (RE) process and the moving estimates (ME) process are k -dimensional Brownian Bridge and the increments of k -dimensional Brownian Bridge, respectively. Under the alternative of a single change, the RE process will have a peak at the change point, while the ME process will have a shift around the point of change.

In the generalized fluctuation tests, with known limiting processes, boundaries can be established such that the probability that the limiting process crosses these boundaries is α . If the empirical fluctuation processes cross the boundaries, the null should be rejected at significance level α . The processes and their boundaries can be presented graphically to visualize the result of the test, and the possible time of a structural change.

The well-known F-tests by Chow (1960) is originally designed to test a single structural change with known time of the change. The regression model is estimated separately in the two sub samples divided by the point of change, the residual sum of squares of this restricted model is compared with that of the unrestricted model

estimated with the full sample. The difference, adjusted by the standard error, follows a χ^2 distribution, if this difference is too big, then the null of no structural change at this known point is rejected. Although this test is for a single change at a known point, the idea can be extended to test for one structural changes of unknown timing. With the computational power we now process, F-statistics can be calculated easily at all potential points of change, the individual F-statistics are aggregated in a single test statistic and the null of no change is rejected if the test statistic is large enough. The aggregation method can be the maximum of the individual F-statistics (the supF test, Andrews 1993), the average of the individual F-statistics (the aveF test), or the logarithm of the average of the exponential of one half the F-statistics (the expF test). Andrews and Ploberger (1994) pointed out that the aveF and expF tests have certain optimal properties. Hansen (1997) developed a method to calculate the asymptotic p values for the tests based on F-statistics.

Zeileis (2005) shows that the existing structural change tests, although developed for different alternatives (single change/unknown multiple changes) and different estimation methods (maximum likelihood/generalized methods of moments/OLS), can be viewed as special cases of the M-fluctuation test (Zeileis and Hornik, 2003). This unified view allows the residual variance to be tested for structural changes jointly with the regression coefficients. Tests based on this idea utilize the likelihood score and are referred as the score-based tests. Similar in ideas to the residual-based CUSUM and MOSUM tests, the score-based tests are based on the sum of likelihood scores either cumulatively or in a moving window, resulting in the score-based CUSUM test and the score-based MOSUM test. This extension is important in many applications of economics or finance, as the variance of the process is usually of main interest in these applications (Zeileis et al., 2010). In our analyses we noticed that the variance of some of the series is not constant over time, taking logarithm of the original series helps stabilize the variance. However, we are curious to see if heteroscedasticity still exists in the transformed series. If structural change in residual variance does exist, the timing of such change will provide additional insight about the nature of the change. As a result, we include the score-based tests in our analyses in this paper.

In practice, the number of structural changes and the times at which they occur are usually unknown and must be estimated from the data (“date” the changes). This can be formulated as an optimization problem. Any m break points b_1, \dots, b_m divide the sample into $m + 1$ segments, within each segment the coefficients of the regression model (1) are constant over time. Hence we have the following piecewise regression model

$$y_t = \beta_{0j} + \beta_{1j}x_{1t} + \dots + \beta_{kj}x_{kt} + \varepsilon_t , \quad (2)$$

for segments $j = 1, 2, \dots, m + 1$. The residual sum of squares of this model is

$$\text{RSS}(b_1, \dots, b_m) = \sum_{j=1}^{m+1} \text{rss}_j,$$

where rss_j is the residual sum of squares in segment j . The problems of dating the changes can be solved by minimizing $\text{RSS}(b_1, \dots, b_m)$ over all possible m change points (b_1, \dots, b_m) . However, solving this problem can be very computationally intensive. In a grid search, the number of calculations needed to find the global minimum is of order $O(T^m)$. Bai (1997) and Sullivan (2002) developed algorithms based on recursive partitioning or joining the segments. Bai and Perron (2003) proposed a modified version of the dynamic programming algorithm originally proposed by Hawkins (2001). This algorithm reduces the number of computations from $O(T^m)$ to $O(T^2)$ for any number of changes m , which makes solving such problems practical. To estimate the number of breaks m , the process above is repeated for all probable values of m , the value m that minimizes certain information criteria is the optimal number of breaks. Commonly used information criteria include the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and a modified version of the BIC (Liu, et al. 1997). This algorithm is used in this paper to date the change points.

The above procedures detect structural changes *ex post*, Hansen (2001) provides an excellent review on these procedures. In recent years, several of the above structural change tests have been extended to *monitoring* structural changes in linear regression models when new observations become available. This approach requires a stable historical period in which no structural change exists, a regression model is identified and estimated using data in this historical period. When new observations become available, the regression model is re-estimated using all available data (the historical period and the new observations), and the estimated results are compared with the estimates from the model estimated with only data in the historical period. If the difference is abnormally large, the null is rejected and one concludes that a structural change occurred. The monitoring approach is very useful in detecting structural change “online”, therefore keeping the regression model valid as time progresses and new data become available. In addition, in monitoring, regression model is identified using only the data in the historical period, therefore it is “correct” in the sense that it is free of the influence of any structural change. The testing approach, on the other hand, uses the whole sample to build the baseline regression model, as such, the regression model estimated is subject to the influence of structural changes if they do exist. Because of this, although not proven theoretically, the monitoring approach should have higher statistical power in detecting structural changes. With the monitoring approach, only the first break will be detected. However, since logically the regression model will need to be updated once a structural change is detected,

the lack of the ability of detecting multiple structural changes does not really pose a problem in practice. Monitoring can be based on recursive estimates of the model coefficients (Chu et al., 1996), the estimates of the model coefficients in a moving window (Leisch et al., 2000), the cumulative sum of OLS residuals (OLS-CUSUM), and the sum of OLS residuals in a moving window (OLS-MOSUM). We use all four tests in this paper to monitor structural changes. The monitoring method requires a “stable” historical period in which data that are free of structural changes, and the length of this period must be long enough to support reliable estimation, which is not always feasible. In such cases, the more “traditional” testing approach is used with data ranging from a few years before and a few years after the games to test for structural changes. We present the results of monitoring and testing in two sections.

3 The data

The data used in this paper are the monthly number of air travel passengers to the host cities of ten recent Olympic games. It has been argued that media coverage of the Olympics leverages the tourism legacy (Preuss, 2004; Duran, 2002; Li and McCabe, 2013, Chalip, 2000). Since the media coverage of the Olympics is much higher in the US than in other countries, we consider US originated passengers and passengers originated outside of the US separately. Some Olympic sites were omitted in one or both series due to lack of available data or because no single dominant airport served the city, such as Nagano, Japan.

The monthly air passenger volume originating from the US to each Olympic site was obtained from the Research and Innovative Technology Administration (RITA) that coordinates the U.S. Department of Transportation Research Programs (RITA, 2018). The US originating arrivals were subtracted from the total international arrivals.

The total international arrivals for London, England was obtained from Heathrow Airport Holdings, formerly British Airports Authority (BAA Traffic Statistics, 2018). Three major airports serves London: Heathrow, Stansted and Gatwick, among them Heathrow receives an average of 76% of non-US international arrivals to London for the period 2003 through 2010, the last year data were available for all three airports separately. For the period of interest, only Heathrow airport has complete data on non-US international arrivals to London, so Stansted and Gatwick are not included. For US originating arrivals to London, Heathrow, Stansted, and Gatwick data are all available from RITA. Total international arrivals for Sydney, Australia was obtained from the Department of Infrastructure and Transport of Australia (2018). The Turin, Italy data were obtained from Assaeroporti Associazione Italiana Gestori

Aeroporti (2018). The Vancouver, Canada data were obtained from the Vancouver Airport Authority (YVR, 2018). The Rio De Janeiro data were obtained from SBGL - Aeroporto Internacional do Rio de Janeiro/Galeão (2018). The host cities, the origination of the passengers (US and non US), the span of the series available for analyses and the dates of the games can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Host Cities, Event Dates, and Time Span

Host	Origination	Begin	Event Date	End
Barcelona	US	1/1990	8/1992	2/2014
Atlanta	US	1/1990	8/1996	2/2014
Atlanta	non US	1/1990	8/1996	3/2018
Sydney	US	1/1990	9/2000	2/2014
Sydney	non US	1/1990	9/2000	3/2018
Athens	US	1/1990	8/2004	2/2012
Beijing	US	1/1990	8/2008	2/2014
London	US	1/1990	8/2012	2/2014
London	non US	1/2003	8/2012	3/2018
Salt Lake City	US	1/1990	2/2002	2/2014
Salt Lake City	non US	1/1990	2/2002	3/2018
Turin	US	1/1990	2/2006	2/2014
Turin	non US	1/2000	2/2006	3/2018
Vancouver	US	1/1990	2/2010	2/2014
Vancouver	non US	1/1992	2/2010	3/2018

All series display strong monthly seasonality, therefore they are seasonally adjusted. In many series, the variability increases over time, as a result, all series are log transformed to alleviate heteroscedasticity. The following Autoregressive models with different orders are identified for different series (the correspondence between the models and the series can be found in Table 7):

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \varepsilon_t, \quad (3)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (4)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 Y_{t-2} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (5)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 Y_{t-2} + \alpha_4 Y_{t-4} + \alpha_8 Y_{t-8} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (6)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_{11} Y_{t-11} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (7)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_{12} Y_{t-12} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (8)$$

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \alpha_{12} Y_{t-12} + \alpha_{13} Y_{t-13} + \varepsilon_t, \quad (9)$$

where Y_t is the log transformed travel volume of month t , Y_{t-i} is the i -th lag of Y_t ($i = 1, 2, 4, 8, 11, 12, 13$), ε_t is iid $(0, \sigma^2)$.

The analyses in this paper are conducted using R-package “strucchange” (Zeileis et al. 2002) which is available at the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN, <http://cran.R-project.org>).

4 The Monitoring Approach

When it is possible to identify a stable historical period, the monitoring approach is used to detect structural changes. Since the main goal of this paper is to study the effect of the Olympic games, ideally the monitoring period should cover a few years before to a few years after the games in order to detect the structural change around the time of the games. Consequently, the historical period should end a few years before the games, while long enough to support reliable identification and estimation of the models. Among the series we analyze in this paper, stable historical periods are possible for the following series: Athens US, Atlanta US, Atlanta non US, London Heathrow US, London Heathrow non US, Sydney US, and Vancouver non US. The results of the series analyzed using the monitoring approach are presented in this section.

Using the historical period data, standard OLS procedures are used to identify, estimate, and validate the regression models. The identified model for each series, the p -values of the F-tests (F -sig), the estimated coefficients with their p -values (in parentheses), R^2 , the p -value of the Ljung-Box test with 12 lags, and the sample sizes, are summarized in Table 2. From this table, we can see that with very few exceptions, the coefficients of the regression models are significant at 5% level, the R^2 are moderate to high (a mean-only model is identified for the Vancouver non US series therefore R^2 is zero). The p -values of the Ljung-Box test (“LB(12)” in the table) show that the residuals are not correlated for any series, this observation is consistent with the residual ACF and PACF (omitted).

Table 2: Estimated Regression Models-Historical Periods

Series	Intercept	Y_{t-1}	Y_{t-2}	Y_{t-11}	Y_{t-12}	R^2	F-sig	LB ₁₂	n
Athens US	0.98(.00)	0.51(.00)		.26(.00)		.72	0	.13	105
ATL US	0.24(.56)	0.96(.00)				.88	0	.87	32
ATL non US	1.44(.00)	0.37(.04)	0.34(.02)			.76	0	.82	32
LHR US	1.16(.02)	0.65(.00)			0.15(.02)	.56	0	.31	76
LHR non US	2.98(.00)	0.34(.01)	0.21(.08)			.30	0	.97	61
Sydney US	2.14(.00)	0.52(.00)				.27	0	.21	64
Van non US	5.19(.00)					.00	0	.53	30

The identified models are then tested for structural changes in the historical periods. The results of various structural change tests are summarized in Table 3. The p -values of the tests show that with two exceptions, namely, the Rec-CUSUM tests on Athens US (p -value=.03) and Vancouver non US (p -value=.04), all tests are not significant at 5% level, therefore the identified regression models are considered break-free in their respective historical periods. These models are used to detect structural

changes in the subsequent monitoring periods.

Table 3: Structural Change Tests-Historical Periods

Test	Athens US		ATL US		ATL non US		LHR US		LHR non US		Sydney US		Van non US	
	Stat	<i>p</i>	Stat	<i>p</i>	Stat	<i>p</i>	Stat	<i>p</i>	Stat	<i>p</i>	Stat	<i>p</i>	Stat	<i>p</i>
Rec-CUSUM	0.99	0.04	0.68	0.28	1.03	0.03	0.72	0.22	0.58	0.45	0.48	0.67	0.94	0.05
OLS-CUSUM	0.89	0.41	0.72	0.68	0.89	0.4	0.86	0.45	0.62	0.84	0.63	0.82	0.88	0.43
Rec-MOSUM	0.96	0.30	1.06	0.23	1.15	0.15	0.99	0.28	0.8	0.42	0.69	0.50	0.89	0.35
OLS-MOSUM	0.86	0.31	0.79	0.37	0.79	0.37	0.73	0.41	0.88	0.3	0.62	0.50	0.8	0.36
RE	1.00	0.60	0.72	0.90	1.13	0.39	0.94	0.72	1.02	0.57	0.67	0.94	0.88	0.43
ME	1.07	0.23	0.78	0.42	0.64	0.54	1.06	0.24	0.88	0.37	0.66	0.50	0.8	0.36
Score-CUSUM	0.74	0.98	1.07	0.49	1.03	0.67	1.23	0.33	0.73	0.99	1.05	0.52	0.99	0.48
Score-MOSUM	0.94	0.34	0.83	0.40	0.92	0.35	1.06	0.25	0.84	0.41	1.12	0.20	0.81	0.39
supF	5.84	0.70	7.17	0.30	10.40	0.20	9.32	0.27	4.67	0.85	3.75	0.78	6.07	0.17
aveF	3.52	0.29	2.33	0.30	4.86	0.12	2.71	0.48	2.19	0.63	0.90	0.83	1.82	0.13
expF	1.90	0.42	1.91	0.20	2.99	0.16	2.05	0.37	1.29	0.68	0.53	0.85	1.21	0.15

All four monitoring procedures detect structural changes around the same time in most of the series. The two exceptions are ATL US, for which no structural change is detected and LHR US, for which only one procedure (OLS CUSUM) detects a structural change. The structural changes detected precede the Olympic games by 1-5 years. The monitoring results are summarized in Table 4. Also given in this table are the historical period and monitoring period for each series analyzed, as well as the dates of the Olympics games.

Table 4: Monitoring Results

Series	Period		Break Dates				Event Date
	Historical	Monitoring	ME	RE	OLS CUSUM	OLS MOSUM	
Athens US	12/1999-8/2000	9/2000-8/2008	9/2001	9/2001	9/2001	12/2001	8/2004
ATL US	5/1991-12/1993	1/1994-8/2000					8/1996
ATL non US	5/1991-12/1993	1/1994-8/2000	2/1995	7/1995	1/1995	4/1995	8/1996
LHR US	5/2002-8/2008	9/2008-2/2014			4/2010		8/2012
LHR non US	8/2003-8/2008	9/2008-8/2016	7/2009	11/2008	2/2009	5/2009	8/2012
Sydney US	1/1990-6/1995	7/1995-9/2004	10/1995	8/1995	8/1995	9/1995	9/2000
Vancouver non US	9/2003-2/2006	3/2006-2/2014	1/2008	11/2008	11/2008	1/2008	2/2010

5 Testing

In the analyses, we found that in some series, stable historical periods with sufficient sample sizes are not possible to identify due to various reasons, including short series

length before the games (e.g., Barcelona 92), too many intervention events during the desired historical period (e.g., Beijing 2008, Turin 2006, etc.). For these series, the monitoring approach does not apply, and all available data in suitable ranges are used to build the regression model and test for structural changes. The results of this approach are presented in this section. The series analyzed using the testing approach are: Barcelona US, Beijing US, Sydney non US, Vancouver US, Turin US, Turin non US, Salt Lake City US, and Salt Lake City non US. The regression models identified for all series, the estimated coefficients with p -values of the t-tests (in parentheses) and F-test, R^2 , the p -value of the Ljung-Box test of 12 lags, and the sample sizes, are summarized in Table 5 below. Once the regression models are identified, they are tested using multiple structural change tests, the test statistics and the p -values of the tests are summarized in Table 6. If the tests detect structural changes, the Bai & Perron (2003) procedure is used to estimate the number and date(s) of the break(s). The breaks, their 95% confidence intervals, along with other relevant information, are summarized in Table 7.

Table 5: Estimated Regression Models-Testing

Series	Intercept	Y_{t-1}	Y_{t-2}	Y_{t-4}	Y_{t-8}	Y_{t-12}	Y_{t-13}	R^2	F-sig	LB ₁₂	n
BCN US	1.52(.00)	.59(.00)						.42	0	.02	64
PEK US	.33(.00)	.93(.00)						.95	0	.90	109
SLC US	1.12(.00)	.86(.00)				.35(.00)	-.40(.00)	.76	0	.65	122
SLC non US	.05(.76)	.67(.00)	.38(.00)	-.33(.00)	.27(.00)			.91	0	.46	77
Sydney non US	.38(.10)	.59(.00)	.34(.00)					.83	0	.35	97
Turin US	1.03(.00)	.60(.00)				.20(.00)		.60	0	.21	130
Turin non US	.18(.34)	.96(.00)						.85	0	.80	99
Van US	.77(.05)	.70(.00)				.15(.05)		.60	0	.66	97

Table 6: Structural Change Tests

Test	BCN US		PEK US		SLC US		SLC non US		SYD non US		Turin US		Turin non US		VAN US	
	Stat	p	Stat	p	Stat	p	Stat	p	Stat	p	Stat	p	Stat	p	Stat	p
Rec-CUSUM	0.62	0.37	1.79	0	1.31	0	0.93	0.06	0.76	0.17	0.45	0.75	0.63	0.35	0.49	0.66
OLS-CUSUM	1.11	0.17	1.12	0.16	0.8	0.54	1.12	0.17	0.89	0.4	1.11	0.17	1.01	0.26	0.86	0.45
Rec-MOSUM	1.07	0.22	1.84	0.01	1.32	0.04	1.35	0.03	1.06	0.22	1.59	0.01	1.11	0.18	1.48	0.01
OLS-MOSUM	1.19	0.06	0.67	0.46	0.93	0.25	0.9	0.28	0.93	0.25	0.83	0.33	0.8	0.35	1.43	0.01
RE	1.07	0.37	1.45	0.06	1.15	0.45	1.66	0.02	1.25	0.24	2.47	0	1.16	0.35	1.57	0.04
ME	0.96	0.28	1.31	0.04	1.51	0.01	1.7	0.01	1.37	0.03	2.2	0.01	1.03	0.26	1.58	0.01
score-CUSUM	1.48	0.07	1.33	0.17	1.08	0.66	1.5	0.09	1.25	0.31	1.06	0.51	1.06	0.61	1.49	0.09
Score-MOSUM	1.26	0.1	0.93	0.33	1.23	0.15	1.19	0.17	1.28	0.1	0.89	0.36	1.11	0.22	2.32	0.01
supF	8.19	0.2	16.28	0.01	9.97	0.38	28.97	0	11.99	0.11	54.44	0	12.41	0.09	19.7	0
aveF	2.11	0.36	6.54	0.01	6.05	0.13	5.62	0.07	5.52	0.08	6.44	0.01	4.23	0.18	7.94	0.01
expF	2.03	0.18	5.05	0.01	3.4	0.22	10.47	0	3.49	0.1	22.94	0	3.77	0.08	6.89	0.01

6 Dating the structural changes

If a structural change is detected in the monitoring period, or if there are strong reasons to support that structural changes exist, the approach by Bai and Perron (2003) is used to estimate the number and location of the structural changes in the combined period including the historical and monitoring periods.

The main idea of Bai and Perron (2003) approach of estimating the number and date(s) of the break(s) is that of an exhaustive grid search. Consider m possible breaks:

- For $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$:
 - place the i breaks on all possible dates, estimate the resulting regression model, the break date(s) that minimize the residual sum of squares (RSS) are the optimal i break date(s).
- The number of breaks that minimizes BIC across all $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ is the optimal number of breaks.

Grid searches are generally computationally intensive, to find the optimal breaks, the number of operations required by a grid search is of order $O(T^m)$ and quickly becomes intractable with the increase of T and m . Bai and Perron's algorithm is based on dynamic programming and reduces the number of operations to $O(T^2)$, therefore makes the estimation of break dates feasible when m is large. The estimated breaks are summarized in Table 7, in which the names of the series, the periods analyzed, the number of breaks, the estimated dates of the breaks and their 95% confidence intervals, the event dates, and the regression model used are listed. The same dating procedure is applied on the series analyzed using the testing approach, the results are also included in this table.

7 Examples

To demonstrate the procedures used in this paper, the detailed results for two series (Sydney US and Vancouver US) are presented in this section. Sydney US is analyzed using the monitoring approach, and Vancouver US is analyzed using the testing approach. The detailed results of the other series are available upon request.

7.1 Sydney US

Sydney hosted the summer Olympics in September 2000. In this section we analyze the travel volume from the US to Sydney. The data available range from January

Table 7: Estimated Breaks

Series	Period	# of Breaks	Break Dates	95% C.I.	Event Date	Lags	Model
Athens US	12/99-8/08	2	4/2001 10/2003	9/00-6/01 6/03-8/04	8/2004	1 & 11	(8)
Atlanta US	5/91-8/00	0	NA	NA	8/1996	1	(5)
Atlanta non US	5/91-8/00	1	6/1993	5/93-6/94	8/1996	1 & 2	(6)
Heathrow US	5/02-2/14	2	8/2008 3/2011	5/06-1/09 12/10-09/11	8/2012	1 & 12	(9)
Heathrow non US	8/03-8/16	2	3/2008 4/2011	12/05-8/08 3/11-5/12	8/2012	1 & 12	(9)
Sydney US	1/90-9/04	2	6/1995 7/2002	3/95-9/95 2/02-1/03	9/2000	1	(9)
Sydney non US	9/96-9/04	2	9/2001 4/2003	11/99-10/01 3/03-2/04	9/2000	1 & 2	(6)
Vancouver non US	9/03-2/14	3	6/2007 4/2009 10/2010	2/07-3/08 1/09-6/09 8/10-2/11	2/2010	mean	(4)
Vancouver US	5/03-2/14	2	1/2008 2/2010	8/07-6/08 7/09-6/10	2/2010	1 & 12	(9)
Barcelona US	5/91-8/96	1	4/1992	2/91-8/93	8/1992	1	(5)
Beijing US	8/03-8/12	4	12/2004 1/2007 5/2008 11/2009	10/04-8/05 2/06-3/07 3/08-12/08 10/09-2/10	8/2008	1	(5)
Salt Lake City US	1/96-2/06	3	3/2001 9/2002 8/2004	4/00-5/01 8/02-12/02 7/04-1/05	2/2002	1, 12 & 13	(9)
Salt Lake City non US	10/99-2/06	2	9/2002 8/2004	8/02-10/02 7/04-9/04	2/2002	1, 2, 4 & 8	(7)
Turin US	12/01-2/10	1	3/2008	9/07-4/08	2/2006	1	(5)
Turin non US	2/02-2/10	2	1/2004 6/2008	4/03-4/04 3/08-8/08	2/2006	1 & 12	(9)

1990 to February 2014, a time series plot of the data is given in Figure 1. Considering the abrupt increase in travel volume around mid 1995, the historical period is set as from January 1990 to June 1995, and the monitoring period is from July 1995 to September 2004. A time series plot of the the data between Jan. 1990 and Sept. 2004 (the historical and monitoring periods) can be found in Figure 10.

Figure 1: Travel Volume Sydney US

An AR(1) model (Equation 5) is identified using the historical period. The model estimates, as well as other statistics, can be found in Table 2. The residual ACF, PACF (Figure 2), and the Ljung-Box test (Table 2) all indicate that the residuals are not serially correlated.

Figure 2: Residual ACF and PACF

Model (5) is tested for structural changes in the historical period and none of the

tests is significant at 5% level (Table 3), therefore it is used to monitor structural changes between July 1995 and September 2004. At $\alpha = 0.05$, all four monitoring procedures detect a structural change near the beginning of the monitoring period (late 1995). The dates of the breaks are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Sydney US Monitoring Results

Test	Break Date
Moving Estimates	Oct. 1995
Recursive Estimates	Aug. 1995
OLS-based CUSUM	Aug. 1995
OLS-based MOSUM	Sept. 1995

From Figure 3, we can see that the overall ME process crosses the boundary in October 1995, Figure 4 shows that the main reason for the break in October 1995 is the lag-1 coefficient, the intercept crosses the boundary at a later date. The Recursive Estimates test shows that the overall process, as well as both coefficients of the regression model, cross the boundary around August 1995 (Figures 5 and 6). The processes for the OLS-based CUSUM test and the OLS-based CUSUM test are plotted in Figures 7 and 8, we can see that the processes cross their 5% boundaries in August and September of 1995 respectively.

Figure 3: Sydney US Moving Estimates Test

Since a break is clearly identified in the monitoring period, we proceed to estimate the number and dates of the breaks in the combined period of both the historical and

Figure 4: Sydney US Moving Estimates Test: Coefficients

Figure 5: Sydney US Recursive Estimates Test

Figure 6: Sydney US Recursive Estimates Test: Coefficients

Figure 7: Sydney US OLS-based CUSUM Test

Figure 8: Sydney US OLS-based MOSUM Test

monitoring periods. From Figure 9, BIC is the lowest at two breaks, and RSS clearly level off after two breaks, hence two breaks are selected.

Figure 9: Sydney US

The two breaks are estimated at June 1995 and July 2002. Their respective 95% confidence intervals are given in Table 9.

From Figure 10, we can see that the travel volume is low and relatively constant before the first break, it begins to increase at a relatively constant rate between the first and the second breaks, reaches a peak around the time of the Olympic games in September 2000, and starts to decrease after that. There is evidence that air travel picks up before the games, and drops back after the games. The second break corresponds to a temporary increase in July 2002. The two breaks divide the series in

Table 9: Sydney US: Break Dates and 95% Confidence Intervals

2.5 %	breakpoints	97.5 %
1995(3)	1995(6)	1995(9)
2002(2)	2002(7)	2003(1)

Figure 10: Sydney US Recursive Estimates Test: Coefficients

three homogeneous segments, model (5) is estimated in these segments and the results are given in Table 10 below, with insignificant coefficients at 10% marked with a *.

Table 10: Estimates in Segments: Sydney US

Segment	Intercept	lag1
1	2.074	0.536
2	1.633	0.651
3	3.942	0.143*

7.2 Vancouver US

Vancouver hosted the winter Olympics in February 2010. In this section we analyze the air travel volume to Vancouver originated from the US. Data from January 1990 to February 2014 are available for analyses (Figure 11), however, in our initial analyses, we found that the 9/11 terrorist attacks in 2001 and the SARS epidemic in 2003

affected travel volume significantly. A long enough period without structural breaks cannot be identified before the games, therefore the data between May 2003 and February 2014 are used to test for structural changes. The data in this period is plotted in Figure 27.

Figure 11: Time Series Plots

Using data between May 2003 and February 2014, an AR model with lags 1 and 12 is identified (Equation 9). The estimated coefficients and other important statistics are given in Table 5. The residual ACF , PACF (Figure 12), and the Ljung-Box (12) test result (Table 5) all show that the residuals are not serially correlated.

Figure 12: Residual ACF and PACF

Model (9) is tested using the data between May 2003 and February 2014 with various tests for structural change, all tests are significant at 5% level, except the recursive

CUSUM test and the OLS-based CUSUM test. The test results are summarized in Table 6. The recursive CUSUM and the OLS-based CUSUM tests, although not significant, their empirical fluctuation processes both peak around early 2008 (Figures 13 and 14).

Figure 13: Vancouver US

Figure 14: Vancouver US

The Recursive MOSUM process and the OLS-based MOSUM process show very similar pattern: the processes crosses the boundary around late 2008, and crosses again early-to-mid 2009, indicating two structural changes (see Figures 15 and 16).

The recursive estimates process crosses the boundary around mid-2009 and mid 2010, indicating two breaks at these two time points. There is also a peak in the process around early 2008, although this break is not significant at 5% level (Figure 17).

Figure 15: Vancouver US

Figure 16: Vancouver US

The recursive estimates procedure is based on the recursive estimate of the regression coefficients, so empirical fluctuation processes can be calculated for individual regression coefficients, which offers additional insights about the nature of the structural changes. The coefficients processes indicate that the structural change is in the lag-12 coefficient but not in the intercept and the lag-1 coefficient, because only the process for the lag-12 coefficient crosses the boundary around mid-2009 and mid 2010, the other two processes do not cross their respective boundaries (Figure 18).

Figure 17: Vancouver US

Figure 18: Vancouver US

The moving estimates process crosses the boundary multiple times between around late 2008 and mid 2009, indicating multiple breaks around these time points (Figure 19). Similar to the recursive estimate test, the moving estimates procedure is based on

the moving estimate of the regression coefficients, so empirical fluctuation processes are available for individual regression coefficients. Similar to the recursive estimates results above, the structural change is only in the lag-12 coefficient, but not in the intercept and the lag-1 coefficient. We can see from Figure 18 that the the lag-12 coefficient process crosses the boundary between late 2008 and mid 2009, while the other two processes stay within their respective boundaries.

Figure 19: Vancouver US

Figure 20: Vancouver US

The score-based tests (Score-based CUSUM and score-based MOSUM) are based on the likelihood scores, similar to the recursive estimates and moving estimates tests, processes for individual regression coefficients are available, in addition, the process for the error variance can also be calculated, so in addition to detecting structural

changes in the regression coefficients, they are useful in detecting heteroscedasticity in the noise. The overall Score-based CUSUM process crossed the boundary late 2009 and mid 2010, indicating two structural breaks (Figure 21). A detailed look at the coefficients reveals that the process for the lag-12 coefficient crosses the boundary late 2009 and mid 2010, while the processes for the intercept, the lag-1 coefficient, and the variance all stay within their respective boundaries, therefore the structural change is in the lag-12 coefficient, and there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity (Figure 22). The score-based MOSUM test shows similar results: the overall process crosses the boundary around mid 2008 and late 2009, indicating two breaks around these two time points (Figure 23). The processes for the coefficients and the variance show that the structural break is in the lag-12 coefficient, whose process crosses the boundary mid 2008 and late 2009, and there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity (Figure 24).

Figure 21: Vancouver US

The F-test is also used to detect the breaks, it indicates at least three breaks, around mid 2009, late 2010, and early 2011 (Figure 25).

Since most of tests detect structural breaks, we proceed to date these breaks. From Figure 26, we can see that BIC is minimized at one break while RSS clearly levels off at two breaks. We notice that the BIC value at two breaks is only slightly higher than BIC at one break, therefore two breaks seem to be a reasonable choice, this is also consistent with most of the tests results above. The dates of the breaks are estimated as January 2008 and February 2010. The break dates and their respective 95% confidence intervals are given in Table 11, and plotted in Figure 27. It can be seen from this plot that the travel volume peaks at the first break (January 2008), and starts to increase again before the second break (February 2010), therefore there is evidence that travel volume increased before the 2010 winter Olympics.

Figure 22: Vancouver US

Figure 23: Vancouver US

Figure 24: Vancouver US

Figure 25: Vancouver US

Figure 26: Vancouver US

Figure 27: Vancouver US

Table 11: Vancouver US: Break Dates and 95% Confidence Intervals

2.5 %	breakpoints	97.5 %
2007(8)	2008(1)	2008(6)
2009(7)	2010(2)	2010(6)

The two breaks separate the time period into three segments, the regression model (9) is estimated in the three segments and the estimated coefficients are given in Table 12, the estimates that are not significant at 5% are marked with a “*”.

Table 12: Estimates in Segments: Vancouver US

Segment	Intercept	lag1	lag12
1	0.9427	0.3612	0.4602
2	2.8575	0.7670	-0.3126*
3	1.1166*	0.2538	0.5350

8 Summary and Discussions

In this paper, we employ structural change tests to detect Olympic tourism legacy and estimate its timing. Regression models are built for air travel volume to eight recent Olympics host cities, and the models are tested using various structural tests. Significant changes in the structure of the regression models indicate changes in air travel volume. Changes in the vicinity of the time of the games offer evidence of the existence of the legacy. The analyses are done using one of the two approaches, depending on if it is possible to identify a stable historical period which contains no structural change. The monitoring approach is used if a stable historical period can be identified, otherwise the structural change tests are used to test for structural changes in the whole period. If structural changes are detected, the number and date(s) of the structural change(s) are estimated using the algorithm proposed by Bai & Perron (2003). For most of the series analyzed, structural changes are detected 1-5 years before the events, hence there are some evidence that air travel volumes change in a significant way before the Olympics. However this is not evidence of causation, and sometimes the effect is confounded with other events, such as the SARS pandemic, or the 9/11 terrorist attacks. This paper offers useful insights on the impact of major events on air travel volume, and applies a novel approach in tourism analytics.

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